

Identity Transformation by Artists Transferring to Musawarah Discussion Community

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: January 26, 2023</p> <p>Accepted: April 27, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Transformation, Community, Hijrah, Lifestyle</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7872777</p>	<p><i>This research is aimed at exploring the identity transformation undergone by artists who “hijrah” or make a transfer of lifestyle within a Young Person’s Discussion Community called Musawarah. This community is based on a lifestyle that is “Sakinah Mawaddah Warohmah” meaning a Place /condition of Peace/ serenity, all Encompassing Love and Spiritually Blessed. The group consists of 19 males and 6 females originating from the middle class who have made a conscious decision to change their lifestyle. The theoretical perspective used for this research is a phenomenological approach based on in depth interviews while the research method used is a qualitative research method consisting of data collection and in depth interviews. The research results found that the artists in the Musawarah Discussion Group went through 6 phases in making the decision to transfer including pre-transfer, stimulation, selfisolation, self-doubt, transfer and post-transfer. Research results indicate that the concept held by the artists was one of Conversion-Reversion. The meaning of “hijrah” in this case does not mean that these artists take on an entirely new identity but that they have returned to the situation they were in prior to becoming artists with all its popularity and glamour and have become more religious than they were before. The identity transformation of these transferring artists is an unfinished or ongoing transfer towards awareness of their self existence as a total personality who has returned or moved away from bad things to that which is good.</i></p>

Introduction

Before the word hijrah came into popular usage, the word taubat was used to mean returning to religion or the right way. The word hijrah in the Quran is translated as transferring or moving location as in the context of Islamic history where it explains the process of moving from Makkah to Madinah made by the Prophet Muhammad (Peace and Blessings be upon Him) with his followers to avoid pressure from the unbelieving members of The Quraishi clan in 662 AD. In spite of this there has been a development of the broadening of its meaning by Islamic groups to mean moving away from unislamic practices to those which are more islamic.

These days hijrah has gained greater attention from researchers from a variety of sciences. One example of this according to Dewi (2020) is in the communication field where the use of the word hijrah has a connection with the condition of the human psyche (Sartaj et al., 2021), and another is hijrah and its connection with sociology (Sifat & Shafi, 2021). Hijrah in its literal translation can mean ‘moving location /shifting stance’. With regard to the world of research specifically this idea of movement invites a multi-range of disciplines to dig even further into what reality lies within the field of Communication Science whereby there is a process in which two or more persons form a significant consensus (Mulyana & Rakhmat, 1990) and which becomes the basis for the hijrah phenomenon in this research

These days ‘Hijrah’ is interpreted as the process of moving away from one behaviour which is not in line with islamic law to one that is. This is something often done by artists. By using a simple way of understanding we can see that the meaning is to change the lifestyle to something positive that tends away from a previous lifestyle outside the norms of religion towards a lifestyle along the lines of religious and sosio-cultural norms and even the law (Croucher, 2008). This hijrah phenomenon amongst artists began around 2013 when the singer Dewi Sandra who beforehand had worn vulgar clothing decided to wear modest clothing and the hijab.

Artists are often seen as role models who have a lifestyle worthy for fans to follow. This means that artists are considered superior and are idolized by fans. By using the bullet effect theory, artists can easily influence fans within a narrow scale and the public on a broader scale. Artists have a self identity which they present when performing on stage. This is clarified in a research made by Lau (2016) based on how Jackie Chan (the Hong

Kong born artist), who formed an identity of himself through action films and another simpler identity of himself through activities on social media which showed him dressed in a T shirt and sneakers and wearing a medical mask. This confirmed Jackie Chan's image as a simple person with a high level of social empathy and caused Jackie Chan fans to follow his lifestyle.

The forementioned situation is similar to the condition of artists in Indonesia. At present there are a number of artists who have emerged with religious identities for themselves and are spreading the Islamic religion through missionary activities. The missionary activities performed by these hijrah artists are usually centered around the story of their point of return or hijrah. The story functions as a strong magnet in their careers as missionary artists. This is because, without introducing themselves, the public have previous knowledge about them so that it is easier for the artists to motivate people through preaching. In the past, the entertainment world was synonymous with the word hedonism. All the behaviour and lives of these artists and actors become interesting to be discussed because of their public popularity.

In the entertainment world artists compete for public attention. The attention given by the public is important for their continued existence. Without the public and media attention there is nothing interesting to talk about. Since the emergence of hijrah role models many have become *ustadz/ustadzah* (religious teachers) appearing on tv screens as part of religious programs or as advertising stars for products labelled as *halal* or religiously permitted products. As well as this the artists have also begun to change the content of the uploads to social media from items about their personal life to filling their content with *hadiths* (sayings and activities of the Prophet Muhammad (Peace and Blessings Be Upon Him) and by also doing religious social activities.

This form of self identity could be considered as the artists' concept of self while the hijrah itself is the transformation of self identity. (Wrench et. al., 2006). The phenomenon of transforming one's self identity by artists seems to have had a domino effect. Dewi (2020) explains that in reality the phenomena of hijrah in the 2000s was a second wave of hijrah conditions. This has a connection with the advancement of information and communication technology. The domino effect was understood from a statement by the missionary and researcher Oki Setiana Dewi who had a deep understanding of the Islamic world and its development. She said that the hijrah condition first appeared in the 1980s and developed with the emergence of new *Pesantrens* (Islamic schools) and and the first waves of strong urban drift. From the history of environmental conditions and freer lifestyles outside the guidelines of religion in big cities at the time, the entry to cities by students from these schools gave impetus to the development of hijrah in Indonesia. This idea is supported by Rachman et al. (2019).

In step with this development, those in the world of Indonesian television became aware that the demand for programs with religious concepts or themes increased and many programs included hijrah artists as guests in order to increase ratings. At the same time it seemed that the 4 self identities of the artists themselves changed and became permanent features within the artists. (Dewi, 2020). Because of this change of self identity the artists were able to bring the fans to join in this hijrah. This phenoenon can be explained by the symbolic interaction theory formulated by George Herbert Mead and developed by Herbert Blumer.

The theory of interactionism as formulated by Mead (Mead, 1934; Mulyana, 2018:284- 285) stressed the importance of its significance in the formation of self identity. The symbolic interaction as formulated by Herbert Blumer (1969) is based on three principles as follows:

1. Humans react to an object based on the significance they give that object in relation to their selves.
2. That significance is gained based on their own social interaction with other people.
3. These significant points change in line with how the social interaction proceeds.

Symbolic interaction is identic with a person's interaction with his/her social environment. Humans don't only react to the actions of other people but also analyze and define every action of the other person.

George Herbert Mead stated that symbolic interaction forms the basis for the development of thought concepts and communication that shape society (Aksan et al., 2009). Nigul Aksan underlined that a person doesn't hold to an understanding about a thing but that social actors form that understanding and it is agreed upon in the person's style of thinking.

Habermas (2010) stated that the present condition of the people can be said to be one of being post-secular compared to being the return of the religious thinking which represents an antithesis from a secular public which regards religion as the enemy of science (Staudigl & Alvis, 2016), an obstruction to the development of rationality (Madung, 2016). Post-secularism can be described as a form of criticism as raised by Habermas

towards the viewpoint of Max Weber of the understanding of a third type of secularisation described in the article of Jose Cassanova (Madung, 2016). Habermas was aware that to become religious did not change the paradigm to be a conservative one but that in fact today's public (in that case the European public) were becoming even more aware that religion was not a path leading to crimes of morality and that it did not represent a restraint to the maturation of oneself.

The secular viewpoint slowly disappeared from the condition of those in certain groups of the artistic people in Indonesia because, as mentioned before, at present artists who had the image of having secular lifestyles had undergone change that marked them with an identity that was in tune with the public's condition. Along with this came having the principles of shying away from worldly things and giving rise to many missionary organizations whose membership contained artists. It is not uncommon to find a public figure being held up as a role model for a number of people in their daily lives. To air the new goings on in their daily lives, celebrities use cyberspace to keep in touch with their fans (Annisa, 2018: 40).

The idea of collective representation introduced by Durkheim is suited to how the discussion community of these artists emerged, in that the spiritual experience that developed became the property of the collective and became the basis for formation of a new social group whose entire membership is filled with artists (Scott, 2013: 51). This membership consisting of only artists later indicated a tendency to become an exclusive group. In his writing, Pratt (2007) stated that the paradigm of exclusivity tends to divide itself into three types: the first is the open type, the second is closed and the third is the exclusive group that is extreme.

At present there is a missionary discussion community called 'Musawarah' which is an acronym of the words 'Muda, Sakinnah, Mawaddah, Warahmah' (young, peaceful, affectionate, blessed) which has become a missionary and discussion community which is filled with Indonesian artists. This Musawarah group was chosen as it highlights that those in artistic circles tend to choose Islamic discussion groups that are of the exclusive type, and do not get exposure, and are even of the 22.5% of communities that are not affiliated with a major Islamic Organization (Dewi, 2020). In other words, artists seem unwilling to follow discussion groups which are open due to high feelings of individuality, wish for privacy, and their individual busy schedules (Ali & Purwandi, 2017). The Musawarah Discussion Community as a group of/for hijrah celebrities implies that it is of the first type, an open social group. This is because the majority of the discussions that take place are open to the public but, not just anyone can actually join the group.

Even this group has a strong influence on the lower strata of the public. They generally have a group of fans spread across a wide range of ages, professions, religion and ethnicities. Whatever happens to them will become a guideline for their fans in the activities of their daily lives.

These artists who have made this hijrah have to a certain extent replaced the role of proper religious teachers and religious leaders on television in providing spiritual guidance. Artists who have fame and made a name for themselves are more readily believed and become a source of information in research into and finding understanding about Islam. In spreading their message the hijrah artists usually focus their narrative around their personal hijrah. The narrative has a strong magnetic effect on the missionary career of these artists. This is because the artists are known without having to be introduced and it becomes easier for them to perform their missionary activities.

The stages of the artists hijrah become a phenomenon that would be interesting to research further so that the public can have a more comprehensive understanding of it. The phenomenon that is meant here is the trend to make this kind of hijrah by artists who form a concept of themselves as spreaders of a religious message. Also of interest is the artists' concepts of self both before and after making the hijrah to the Musarawah Community, what their motives are for making the hijrah, how they put their hijrah concepts into practice within the Musawarah Community, how the hijrah artists see the significance of their communication experience, and how the stages of their identity transformation proceeded inside the Musawarah Community.

The artists transformation of identity could very well include physical transformations such as changes in choice of apparel and changes in personal relationships. However these physical changes could be brought about by environmental pressures that tend towards changes in activities and could lead to psychological transformation (Mulyana & Kadri, 2019). According to Musgrove (1977:15) changes in awareness occur at the same time as where the relationship between the self and social experience are interpreted in hindsight and is seen in a new light. According to Mead, (1968) Awareness is the core of self while according to Musgrove (1977) it is the source of self.. Changes in awareness and the concept of self by the artists after going through the hijrah process is what is meant as Transformation of Identity in this writing.

In accordance with Strauss' (1959:91-92) book *The Method of Qualitative Research* (Mulyana, 2022) states that the transformation of identity involves a psychological change whereby the subject becomes a personality which is different than before. Because of this, the transformation of identity implies that there is a new evaluation of one's self and others, of events, actions and objects. (Wrench et. al., 2006). Transformation of identity like this makes it possible for a reorientation and a revision of interactions within the hijrah artist's social community.

The subjects of this research are artists who have already decided to make the hijrah. Before making the hijrah and when their popularity as artists was at its peak the artists had a variety of activities, experiences and traditions handed down from generation to generation which Schutz described (Musgrove 1977:109) as a recipe of knowledge, or as Berger and Luckmann (1990:58) stated had been socially constructed. This experience plays an important part as the guideline for people to go on with their daily lives. According to Musgrove (1977:15), the awareness changes when the relationship between self and this social experience is reanalyzed and seen in a new light. Musgrove's theory is supported by Denzin (1987:11) 7 who defined transformation as a process whereby a person actively takes on a new sense of self, a new self language, enters new relationships with other people and forms new bonds with its own social order. In this context, according to Strauss (as stated in Mulyana, 2002), other important people become very important to the individual who has undergone the change and they become partners in the building of the secondary identity (Berger & Luckmann 1990:236).

Significant others have an important role in the transformation of an artist who is making the hijrah and in enabling them to communicate with others. They have an important role in the ongoing process of consolidating the reality factors which are deemed as parts of being an identity (Berger & Luckmann, 1966:170). By becoming a member of a certain group a person defines his self to himself and to those outside himself (Bottomley, 1979:22). The response and the different behaviour of these others will significantly influence the direction and rythmn of the artists in achieving a transformation of identity. Because of this we can understand that the transformation of identity is not the same for each individual artist.

Different patterns of identity transformation are possible as every individual interacts differently inside the community and within their own social environment and can also respond to those environments with ways that also differ, as assumed in the Symbolic Interaction Theory. They could even avoid discussion topics and behaviour which they consider to be unsuited to the new identity that they are trying to build.

“In conversation the objectifications of language becomes objects of individual consciousness . . . In order to maintain subjective reality effectively, the conversational apparatus must be continual and consistent . . . One cannot remain a Muslim outside the 'umma of Islam . . . “ (Berger and Luckmann, 1966:173,174,178).

According to Mead (1934) and Cooley (1983:184), a person's interpretation of an evaluation of himself by another person represents a deciding factor in the formation of a self concept by the subject. For that reason the process of identity transformation by artists who have experienced instability and emptiness in their search for happiness during their period of popularity now increases the dynamics of their character as well as the scope of their social communication. In reference to the concept of self as defined by Mead and Cooley above, it can be assumed that hijrah artists continually evaluate and interpret themselves based on the evaluations of others as they understand them.

Method

This research uses a qualitative method based on phenomenological tradition (Cresswell, 2013). Based on specific characteristics of qualitative research, information is not only aquired through humans but can also be obtained from the observation of events and situations. The subjects of this research are national celebrities who have joined the Musawarah Discussion Group while the object of the research is the significance and the transformation of identity of the artists in the Group. The research subjects include former model and actress of Dutch descent RS. Then there was HR a celebgram born in 1994 and who is now a brand ambassador for a well known cosmetic brand in Indonesia. The number of artists the researcher interviewed was 8 with details as follows:

No	Initial	Gender	Profession	Age
1	RS	M	Actor	40
2	HR	F	Celebgram	29
3	HF	M	Ustadz	33
4	DH	M	Actor	43

5	TW	M	Actor	38
6	RH	M	Actor	36
7	AU	M	Presenter	47
8	FA	F	Presenter	37

Snowball Sampling was used in the research to attain the clearest collection results and information possible. (Johnson & Christensen, 2014). Snowball sampling was based on a purposive sampling technique so that the field data would provide a true picture of the phenomenon being researched. Qualitative research of the subjective experiences of the hijrah artists like this research seem to have still been rarely performed in Indonesia. It is partly because of this that this research was made. The research took two years to make from 2021 – 2023.

Besides interviewing and observing the twelve artists as informants the researcher also interviewed and observed the Ustadz (religious teachers) who provided dakwah (preaching religious information) at the Musawah Discussion Group, especially Ustadz Hilman Fauzi as the key information source. More specifically this research follows the process of identity transformation undergone by the artists performing the “Hijrah”. All the information was attained through in-depth interviews with informants and persons close to them as well as from 9 a number of observations of their activities when they took part in Musawah Discussion Group Activities.

Results and Discussion

The transformation identity of hijrah artists as middle class Indonesians didn't just take place overnight but went through several processes, even though the process(es) of each of these members of Musawah Discussion Group were unique to each individual. An example of this can be based on the following interview by the researcher with one of the artists:

“Each person who joins the Musawah Discussion Group has his / her own story. Their are those who are tired of the world of artists full of sparkle and tinsel and want a peaceful life. I made the hijrah because I experienced a state of boredom in my entertainment industry career and wanted to look for new experiences and to begin again and take a new direction in life.” (RS)

In this research the researcher does not name the artists who became informants in order to protect their individual privacy as some of them felt that their condition before making the hijrah was shameful. Instead the researcher uses initials to refer to these artists and performed in depth interviews to look into the phenomenon of hijrah in greater detail. More specifically the research found that the hijrah transformation that the artists went through consisted of five stages or phases including : pre-hijrah, stimulation, self-isolation, self-doubt, and post-hijrah.

Pre-Hijrah

Before making hijrah many of these Indonesian artists were involved in behaviour unsuited to religious values such as the use of drugs, drinking alcohol and participating in illicit relationships. They were also often involved in controversies that damaged their public image. Following their hijrah, a number of them were able to change and tried to live in line with the teachings of religion and to become better examples for their fans.

For anyone, Hijrah to a better path can bring positive effects to that person's way of life and this has been true for these Indonesian artists too by helping them to find peace in their lives, increasing the quality of their lives and improving the relationships with family and friends. However the hijrah process can also be difficult and full of challenges, especially where a person has to change an ingrained lifestyle and habits.

The pre-hijrah condition of these Indonesian artists varied widely with each individual. However, hijrah to a better way can bring about positive changes in a person and help them to find peace and happiness in their lives and so it has been for the artists who joined into the Musawah Discussion Group. Their condition before this hijrah was filled with activities that were far from a religious condition. Alcohol is a good example of this as the artists were in the habit of drinking alcohol when they finished working on television. In the context of the religion of Islam alcohol is forbidden under Islamic Law as was reported by Abu Dawud who said that the Prophet Muhammad SAW, as Rasulullah (The Messenger of God) declared,

"Wine or alcoholic beverages have been made a cursed material for the one who drinks it, the one who pours it, the one who sells it, the one who buys it, the one who prepares it, the one who asks a person to prepare it, the one who transports it, the one who requests its transport and the one who eats from its sale. " (Reported by

Ahmad (2/25,71), Ath-Thayalisi (1134), AlHakim At-Tirmidzi dalam Al-Manhiyaat (hal: 44,58), Abu Dawud (3674),

According to the informants, artists got involved with alcohol because it was readily available and alcohol provided them with a sense of peace, however temporary. There were even artists from the Musawah Discussion Group that got involved with forbidden narcotics. AU admitted being involved with a lot of drugs during his career as a VJ.

“I mean our proximity to this was very close. We knew the people who had the drugs and when they had them. I think this was one way of God protecting me. Maybe we used to think it was cool.” (AU)

The world of entertainment should always show the good side of the artists to the public. Every artist is sure to have their own personal problems but it's clear that this should not be seen when they are working. Quite often these problems get blown out of proportion to create greater popularity, even where the problem is not really a problem but a gimmick or agenda setting served up as content to increase the popularity of the artist him/herself. It is common for artists to seek ways of relaxing from their heavy schedules by turning to things forbidden by religion such as alcohol, nightlife and drugs. Lyansari (2018) stated that this phase is the phase of unawareness. This lack of awareness is connected with how easy it is for a person to use or consume something because of the influence of their relationships.

In the theory of reason action for example, social influence is one of the factors as to why individuals use or consume something. It is just that under these conditions the motivation to alcohol or even drugs is not based on a real awareness of full control psychologically but rather is influenced by it being a way to relax and search for peace. This researcher uses the phrase ‘to search for peace’ because according to the information source most of the artists 11 who appear on television always appear to be happy as a gimmick but behind that they have high levels of stress.

As people who are often from the middle class, artists also consider that if they don't drink alcohol they will be considered as being unable to keep up with the modern trend. The modern popular term for this is FOMO (fear of missing out) which can literally be interpreted as a person having the feeling they are not up to date with what's happening in society. The importance of always updating one's information amongst artists is because in the world of entertainment if they don't know about developments they fear that they will not be able to produce the right atmosphere for the audience or they fear that they won't be able to provide the content that the audience demands in connection with what is trending at present.

Stimulation

The decision to make hijrah will not occur if there isn't some sort of stimulation or prodding. Each of the artists had a different kind of stimulation but one of the major motivators was their inability to control themselves because of the pressure they experienced in both their professional world and their personal lives. Aside from this, they have also got another motivator in that the artists were taking part in religious programs. Both these motivating pressures were a big part for each of them to make a transformation of identity. Firstly, an artist would make the decision to hijrah because they had a big problem and they couldn't de-escalate it. Beforehand, it was explained that artists would seek out alcohol to calm themselves but as the problems were so deep some artists lacked the motivation to go out of the house.

A stimulant or stimulation is not necessarily the only reason why a person makes a hijrah but could be a supporting factor to the main reason. It could be said that the main factor is the circumstances that cause the individual to make the transfer (Wrench et. al. 2006). In many situations the stimulation comes continuously from a number of directions and combines to force the transformation of identity experienced by the artists. With regard to this research the researcher limits the meaning of ‘stimulant’ as being like different types of lighters that ignite the passion inside the hijrah artists. That is what happened with FA who tried to change her appearance by wearing a hijab, a muslim headcovering. FA put a considerable amount of time into strengthening her hijrah.

“In fact the wish to wear the hijab began nine years ago when I made the Haj (Pilgrimage to Mecca) However, at that time there were a lot of considerations from work issues to what I should wear. I often asked myself why a woman should have to wear a jilbab. If I wore how would my relationships be and how about my work. The good and bad sides had to be taken into account. Sometimes we wait for a sign from God whereas in fact it depends on our contemplation on things that happen to us.”. (FA)

Self-Isolation

In this phase artists find that they feel an aversion to take part in the world of Glamour and Glitter or events filled with entertainment. The condition of isolating oneself represents a critical phase because it could lead to a path with dangerous pitfalls such as leading to the use of drugs. It can't be denied that artists' access to illegal drugs can be considered easy because of the range of their communication network formed through their popularity.

DH admits that from the outset of his marriage he was committed to avoid and not be tempted by a free lifestyle. Even though he sometimes had to meet with friends where there was smoking and drinking he didn't feel tempted. "In fact in that place I could never drink or anything, not even smoking cigarettes, because in reality I didn't like the smell" (DH). Because of this, DH's friends often said that he was pretending to be 'so mr clean'. For DH, his decision to hijrah and to only select shooting offers in line with his life principles represented proof of his meeting with his hidayah (call to follow religious life style).

Besides this, this is a difficult phase for artists to be able to complain about their position to fellow artists. According to DH, the environment of his fellow artist friends was not one of genuine friendship but limited to professionalism. This occurred due to the limited time artists have to spend together so that while they may appear to be friendly with each other on television, such as between Andre Taulany and Entis Sutisna (screen name -Sule), the reality is not like that. According to them, even though the public consider them to be partners who have a strong friendship, the friendship is no more than a gimmick. This Gimmick can be interpreted to mean that the audience is more inclined to accept content wherein artists have a degree of closeness with other artists as it seems more natural, but, in the real world this closeness is difficult to form.

As was stated before, artists have a limited amount of time available to spend on more intimate relationship activities or to hang out with other artists in order to build deeper relationships. Opportunities to do so are difficult to create, especially as whenever they do have time they prefer to spend that time with family.

Unfortunately, when artists are faced with a problem they are unwilling to share their gripes with family. Artists don't want their families to know when they're facing a problem if the problem doesn't involve family. Where the problem faced originates in their personal life or family artists even consider that other people have no role to play in understanding the problem they are facing.

These interfering conflicts of thought can even be made worse by social media. They hint at any conflict that they are experiencing through implicit symbols because, as already mentioned, the artists are hesitant to speak about the problems they are facing to the public fearing the consequences to their public popularity.

Self-Doubt

Contemplation of the situation by the artists gives rise later to an idea. The idea brings back memories of the period before the artists entered the world filled with glitter and glamour, public attention, alcohol, the nightlife and others. Quite a number of Indonesian artists, though not all, had limited lifestyles economically before they became artists. They experienced what Kelsen (1981) described as "liminal condition" indicated by uncertainty about the meaning of life and self, with questions such as who am I / Where am I from? What am I doing? What is my goal in life?

Artists remember going through life without using a self identity and just being themselves. During this phase an artist begins to know what their identity really is. In the world of entertainment artists have to shape an identity of self that no other artist has. This identity of self becomes unique to that artist, and an artist without such an identity becomes difficult for the audience to remember. This specific identity of self is what will be remembered by the public as being who the artist is. For example, AU built an identity for himself as a being skilled as a solitary comedian and often filled comedy sketches on TV. However, nowadays AU has chosen to leave the television comedy stage after deciding to find out more about religious knowledge. "Over the last few years I have no longer performed because lots of sexy females have appeared. They said that these sexy women were brought in only to create a balance but I couldn't accept it." (AU)

In truth, AU had already received the explanation from the television owners about the circumstances surrounding the introduction of sexy women to comedy sketch programs but he was not comfortable with it, especially as he was learning how not to shame other people whereas the guidelines for the comedy sketches required him to do just that. Meanwhile AU still wants to show who he is as a comedian and is still looking for a new way to perform comedy that doesn't shame other people. "I have already found a new recipe for comedy

but it's still in progress. The plan is to upload this new type of comedy on You Tube . When it's ready, we'll see how it goes. (AU)

Changes in personal identity that are too implanted and congealed will cause the artist to forget who they really are in the end. At this point in the phase artists begin to return to their true characteristic self from before they came up with the self identity they wanted to show in the entertainment world. As in the conversion-reversion concept we have seen, the artists return to how they were before and their omissions get more covered up as they begin to see the religious messages in social media such as YouTube. However, in this phase there is still rejection within the artist to return to their original life. This refusal comes because there are still memories connected with things associated with the world of artists. By seeing how calmly the religious teachers present their material via social media, the artists begin to get interested in choosing their path with a teacher or someone who has high religious knowledge.

This desire to meet with an ustadz, kyai or habieb as the religious teacher is meant to ask the myriad of questions about life the artists have. But, as is typical of the axiom for artists who have become the center of public scrutiny, the artists have an aversion to joining a majelis (quranic learning Group) in their local environment due to several fears including: worry about rumours as to why the artist decided to join the majelis. Secondly worry that when they join the majelis its members will see it as an opportunity to make approaches to them. This is the reason why the Musawarah Discussion Group was formed and also the reason why the group tends to have a private or closed character and in this way the discussion could proceed in a maximal way without having to distance oneself from participating inclusively.

Post Hijrah

Finally, the artists have made their hijrah to find their true identity in life. They no longer even care about the popularity they worked so hard to build. Of course that popularity has not fully disappeared but the popularity that they still possess is now used to spread material connected with religious knowledge. Besides sharing with the public, these artists who have made the hijrah and know about the phases involved now have a new target which is to guide other artists who have the same problems they had to join in to religious discussions with the Musawarah Discussion Group.

An understanding of the cycle for the artists' acceptance of ideas about hijrah is not a quick process but a long process that can take months or even years before they decide to make the hijrah. The transformation of identity only relates to the artists who have joined the Musawarah Discussion Group. According to several of the informants, the process and model of each discussion differs depending on the teacher the artists follows.

It can't be denied that hijrah by the artists went hand in hand with them refusing offers to take part in tv programs in which they used to participate as they were no longer suited to their new beliefs after their hijrah. In other words they were now more selective when choosing to take part in programs. It became an important point for artists that when they made the hijrah that it didn't mean there were no opportunities to fill in tv programs. There were still several prominent religious programs that made this possible for artists so that artists were encouraged to make hijrah. As explained by Oki Setiana Dewi in her dissertation, religious teachers who filled preaching programs in tv from the year 2000 to the present were not sought for their knowledge but for the long journey they had taken to become a person of faith. As an example, Dewi stated that at the time Aa Gymn wasn't someone who had a high level of religious knowledge but he had an interesting rhetoric, a good voice and interesting experiences to share. (Dewi, 2020).

In this research hijrah represents a form of the transformation of self that ideally ought to relate to the full range of subjects about an individual. Furthermore, hijrah isn't only about a change in the way of clothing oneself but change that takes place at the highest level of the subjects awareness. Self awareness as put forward by Mulyana (2019) is the essence of the patterns of behaviour, ways of thinking and actions of a person.

Figure 1. The Process of Transformation of Identity by Hijrah Artists

The model that can be seen in Picture 1 shows the flow process of identity transformation. The form of the transformation in that case was based on activities that occurred within the subject's self when the research subjects look for the meaning of life which connects in the way a person sees and adapts to their environment (Croucher, 2008). This can happen because self identity is part and parcel of every person so that when the process of hijrah takes place, the individual transforms in terms of way of thinking or action or even adaptation with his / her environment as was confirmed by the research done by Wrench et. al. (2006).

The concept 'Hijrah' explored in this study can be defined as 'returning' – returning to find one's self and become who the artist was before he/she persevered their way into the world of artists. This turning point represents the peak of the entire hijrah process. According to Ustad Hilman Fauzi, the stepping away is meant as stepping away from a place, situation or thing that is bad towards a place or something that's good. Then changing from bad habits to good habits. Next is moving from the place or situation where it is difficult to find any good to a place where only good is found and finally to leave behind everything that is forbidden by Allah SWT for us his servants.

For the informants the path to hijrah required careful preparation. It required the right strategy and also that the person fill their time with good things and activities until the person arrives at the truest level of hijrah. Just like normal people, artists must have a past, must surely have done wrong, and must have made mistakes. What we are calling hijrah here used to be called taubat (feeling sorry for one's mistakes and endeavouring not to repeat them). In spite of the word taubat meaning returning and the word hijrah meaning to move away, we often consider them to mean the same thing. According to Ustadz Hilman, the artists usually show signs that they have already made hijrah or what is usually called Hijrah Syu'uriah Syu'uriah. It can mean a move away from habits, hobbies or pleasures that are considered not in line with the rules of the religion of Islam. For female artists the first sign of their hijrah is usually marked by the decision to wear a kerudung (head scarf). A change of appearance does, in fact represent a form of hijrah that is the easiest, even though it's done to show the Indonesian public that they are in a phase of performing hijrah.

The issue of wearing specific Islamic clothing in the process of transformation of identity can be symbolically connected with the act of yielding to the syariat (rules, regulations and laws) of Islam. From the interview with

Ustadz Hilman Fauzi, clothing represents the easiest visual sign of hijrah to recognize and is a sign meaning that there has been a change or transfer in the actor's identity. Simple or collective signs or symbols of a male stating that they have made hijrah can be seen by them wearing religious clothing such as long flowing robes etc.

Besides changing one's appearance to become more Islamic, such as by women wearing a kerudung and clothing covering the body parts and limbs and by men wearing loose trousers down to the ankles, other physical changes like growing a beard can be signs of Hijrah Syu'uriah but the main element of Hijrah Syu'uriah is that the artists no longer fill their lives with the pleasures the artists knew before such as nightlife, alcohol and others. In the hijrah, artists are refinding their real self as a follower of Islam and closer to the laws of Islam and theology. They are trying to perform virtuous deeds and leaving off a large part of their artistic attributes by staying away from programs that lead to slander, relinquishing links with conventional banks and using syariah banks, and not listening to commercial western music. The next process they enter is the Hijrah Sulukiyah (Behavioural hijrah).

Sulukiyah can be interpreted as meaning that there are changes in the behaviour of an individual and can be assembled verbally or nonverbally. The verbal communion meant here is interpersonal communication. For example, the word 'akhi' which they use as a greeting between male artists is adopted from the Arabic language and means my brother. This style of communication from the point of view of symbolic interaction is used by the subject to greet someone applying a religious connotation.

Another thing that we can observe is their new nonverbal behaviour such as tending to choose not to shake hands with someone of the opposite sex, especially those who are not family. This form of greeting is more in line with religious norma and shows that the artist has had a change of attitude in order to be recognized more easily as a muslim. The signs of hijrah are not only visible signs but can also include spiritual signs such ways of thinking and belief. Of course these steps vary from artist to artist depending on 'what' motivated the artist to make hijrah and the timing of this occurrence varies from one phase to another.

Supported by their new social environment they the research subjects shift from the profane secular world to a world of holiness (Musgrove, 1977:22). Now religion provides significant meaning to their world which had formerly been difficult to interpret and gives them a sense of comfort and belonging amongst the uncertainty of life. Religious ideas which formerly were on the fringe of their awareness now take an important position and become an ideal aim and a center for their energy (William James in Travisano, 1970:600), “

Conclusion

The transformation of identity by artists in Indonesia represents a process whereby artists return to become their real self, or return to their old identity that had been buried for so long after they had built an identity for themselves in the entertainment world. The aforesaid transformation consist of five stages including: unawareness (pre-hijrah), stimulation, selfisolation, self doubt, and post-hijrah. There is a crucial point between the self doubt and the post hijrah, that is, making a big decision (the turning point of the subjects) before reversing to the "old" self-concept. So the concept of artists making a hijrah is a concept of Reversion. This means that the hijrah here is not that the artists change their identity to something completely new but that the artists return to the condition they were in before they became artists who were entrenched in popularity and the world of artists (even though they do not return fully to their original identity).

This research is not meant to make a generalization to discussion groups outside of Musawarah. Further research could look further into the hijrah model as made by artists in different discussion groups, and also by using another relevant theory and research method so that the transformation of identity model becomes more complete and comprehensive.

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